

MEDIA AND INFORMATION LITERACY SKILLS
OF BAGUIO CITY PUBLIC LIBRARY USERS

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ABSTRACT

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This study looked into the utilization and level of competency in media and information literacy of library users at Baguio City Public Library. It is designed to answer the following questions in particular: 1) What are the different purposes of library users in utilizing the media and information resources; 2) What is the extent of the utilization of media and information resources by library users; 3) What is the level of competencies of media and information skills of library users in terms of the following: a) access to media and information; b) evaluation of media and information; c) use of media and information.

In this study, questionnaires were used as the primary data gathering tool for survey research. The respondents were students, unemployed and employed library users.

The study revealed that most respondents mainly use media and information resources for academic development purposes and followed by personal development and entertainment/recreation purposes. Along with academic development, library users mainly go to the library to study or review

their lessons for incoming periodic examinations and to read references that supplement their studies or school requirements. Print and non-print materials have equal utilization. Only reference books and the internet are utilized to the extent of sometimes, the rest of the library resources are utilized to the extent of rarely. Library users possess an intermediate level of competency in accessing, evaluating, and utilizing media and information resources. There is a significant difference in the level of media and information literacy competencies among the employed, unemployed and the student library users.

Keywords: Media and Information Literacy, Media Literacy, Information Literacy, Level of Competency, Literacy Skills

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INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents an overview of media and information literacy and the related research that would enrich the knowledge and deepen the understanding of literacy and the role of public libraries. It also shows the principles behind the study, the conceptual framework, and the statement of the problem.

Background of the Study

Communication technology, mass media, and the internet continues to evolve every day. Our information sources grow at a rapid rate and accessibility has become easier than ever. However, these opportunities also pose challenges in the field of media and information literacy. So, we need a set of skills and abilities to fully understand what we access and be able to evaluate information and use it. Additionally, the expanding information ecosystem demands us to learn how to filter information. Therefore, there's a need to locate relevant sources, make a distinction between reliable and unreliable information and information sources that are questionable (European Parliament, 2016). It is clearly understood here that we need to have literacy competencies.

The background of literacy started when information literacy was first coined by Paul G. Zurkowski in 1974. He pointed out, information literacy allows an individual to identify, evaluate, and choose the information that matches the

need (Landoy, Popa, Repanovici, 2019). In the field of librarianship, literacy has guided the development of libraries. The Association of College and Research Libraries (ACRL, 2018) defined information literacy as a set of abilities that requires an individual to recognize when they need information and have the ability to locate information, evaluate information, and effectively use the needed information.

Koltay (2011) pointed out the need of media awareness due to emerging digital technologies. The demand to cope with the changing landscape of information and technology lead to the concept of Media and Information Literacy (MIL).

The field of Media and Information Literacy is gaining more attention nowadays. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) created MIL competencies and in 2017 merged the two separate concepts. In addition, UNESCO (2022) defines MIL as a set of competencies that are interrelated that helps people maximize the advantages of the use of media and information and minimize harm in the evolving information, communication landscapes, and digitals. MIL recognizes the role of information and the media in people's everyday lives. It relies on the fundamental rights of freedom of expression and information to empower citizens to understand the functions of the media and other information providers; to evaluate their content critically; to make informed decisions based on evaluated information (UNESCO, 2019).

MIL equips an individual the competencies needed to critically engage with information and other forms of media content, and how to use media and information in a legal and ethical manner. It also covers the institutions that facilitate information and diverse types of content, and the discerning use of digital technologies. The International Federation of Library Association (2012) argues that people need the skill and practice to access, analyze, and communicate information in a variety of forms.

Changing social norms increasingly emphasizes the importance of the skills and competencies of MIL who deal with information and are exposed to a wide variety of information sources. Maharaj (2020) mentioned that in the midst of Corona Virus 2019 (COVID-19) crisis, MIL is more critical than ever. The current digital age combined with the pandemic that has forced people to stay at home and to work from a distance have created an even greater need for connectivity, networking, and interdependence. Even the way we consume news and information has evolved with the changing landscape of media from analog to digital. This situation has also made people more vulnerable to misinformation and disinformation. The new media landscape, which gave birth to social networking sites such as Twitter, Facebook, and TikTok, allows information to be easily shared. This mobility and accessibility of information has created the phenomenon of fake news. Fake news is defined as fabricated information, designed to manipulate people's perceptions of real facts, events, and statements

(Center for Information Technology and Society, 2022). The spread of fake news has dangerous consequences and the only way to battle them is to equip people with the skill and competencies they need to become literate and empowered users and creators of media and information. Furthermore, Schultz (2019) stressed that MIL is a social necessity in light of the massive development of new media resources like social media, electronic news sites, and digital channels. These resources confront individuals with a vast amount of information, technologies, headlines, and varying opinions. Ensuring the awareness of the next generation of how to interact with various forms of media is essential because they convey the information, and the news they will encounter, and producing it is often their responsibility (Al Zou'bi, 2022). As reported, every year, social media users add almost three hundred million new registered accounts, which is approximately five hundred fifty per minute (Schultz, 2019). The increasing number of social media users is a clear indicator of the growing need for MIL in eliminating misinformation and disinformation. The study by Al Zou'bi (2022) reveals the major role of MIL; which plays in combating rumors and false news, exposing false information, developing skills, and strengthening critical thinking among individuals to determine positive and negative messages. Also, it enables individuals to determine between facts and opinions which help to stop the spread of false information and avoid it from reaching a larger audience. In addition, Silva (2009) stressed that the nature of 21st century skills is focusing on an

individual's influence capacity is essential by sharing the acquired knowledge rather than just merely acquiring it. It is essential to keep in mind that MIL never ends with the consumption of information. It works more effectively when it is being shared, produced, and reproduced. Consequently, information that was understood and shared becomes knowledge.

MIL was introduced to secondary education in the Philippines when K to 12 program was passed as a law. The Department of Education (DepEd) has included MIL as core of the subjects in Senior High School. This subject introduces learners to MIL as a channel of communication and a tool for individuals and societies. The main objective is to develop students to be critical thinkers and creative. Further, to become competent producers and responsible users of media and information (Department of Education, 2013). With the focus on equipping young learners with the skill to not only consume information and media content but also to produce them, there is a consistent need for accessible, credible, reliable, and scholarly sources of information such as the library.

The advent of digital technologies does not hinder the library to grow, rather it continuous to evolve by enhancing its services and programs which leads to transformation of library's role to becoming an information-rich environment. Public libraries, together with academic libraries, school libraries and research libraries are at the forefront of promoting information literacy and until expanding it to media literacy. Libraries maintain their value in individuals' learning

processes by instructing and assisting them to find and evaluate a wide range of information sources, in their own library collections, on the web and databases (European Parliament, 2016). Moreover, public libraries are committed to promoting information literacy and media literacy programs in their communities by providing information access and instruction to those who needed them (Huysmans, 2016). Public libraries, with their roles as trusted content providers, community information hubs, and centers of lifelong learning, contribute to a more empowered and equitable society by helping citizens make informed decisions that lead to developments that are inclusive (Grizzle, et al. 2021).

However, based on the study conducted by Labangon and Zabala (2018) among four regions in the country, public libraries were less visible in implementing MIL. In Baguio City, for example, some library users of the Baguio City Public Library lack research skills in locating their media and information needs. The teachers from Irisan National High School were also asking for help from the librarians to share the librarian's knowledge on how to conduct research. This indicates the need for media and information literacy among library users in the community.

Thus, there is a need to conduct this study to help understand and further investigate how the Baguio City Public Library, as a media and information provider in the city, is thriving in this age of technological advancement.

Moreover, this study targets to create a community that values literacy and lifelong learning.

Conceptual Framework

The International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA) and UNESCO (2001) Public Library Manifesto stipulates that one of the roles of public libraries is to facilitate the development of information and computer skills for the community. The goal of the public library is lifelong learning and a literate community. However, in this digital era, the concept of literacy is still being discussed.

As literacy has evolved in different contexts, there has been a significant connection between the terms frequently used to describe it. In the late twentieth century, information literacy, digital literacy, computer literacy, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) literacy, media education, and media literacy were discussed and recognized while MIL was introduced in the modern era at exactly year 2017.

Strategies and conceptual approaches are distinguished traditionally between information literacy, digital literacy and media literacy. UNESCO's composite concept brings these literacies together as a united set of competencies necessary for life and work in today's world. It covers all forms of media and providers of information sources such as libraries, the internet, archives, and

museums (UNESCO, 2020).

Since 2012, the IFLA and UNESCO have collaborated on media and information literacy. These two organizations take the two concepts in tandem, which could broaden the traditional scope of library services to include information literacy. They have stressed the importance of MIL for the cultural development, social development of individuals, societies and communities. MIL has been written in a unitary framework, and librarians are being supported in formulating practical programs that promote MIL development (European Parliament, 2016).

Furthermore, UNESCO is the leading organization in promoting MIL. It empowers individuals to think critically about access to information and practice use of the digital tools. It enables individuals make informed decisions about how they actively participate in freedom of expression, peace building, dialogue, access to information, equality, and sustainable development. MIL initiatives are supported and championed by UNESCO throughout the world to click wisely and think critically. Specifically, strive for enhancing the capacities of educators, information and media professionals, and policymakers, as well as in encouraging member states to devise national MIL strategies and policies (UNESCO, 2022).

Today, MIL has become one of the strongest catalysts for the development of society. In general, there are a large number of information sectors growing rapidly in developing countries. Everyone must think and understand that, for a

developed society, the organization, generation, evaluation, and dissemination of information takes an important effect on people's lives (Rusiana and Naporata, 2021).

The schematic diagram showing the relationship of concepts used in the study research is in Figure 1 which shows how the study was undertaken. The independent variables are library resources specifically the media resources and information resources available at Baguio City Public Library that are utilized by library users to assess the dependent variables. The dependent variables determine the purpose of utilization of media and information resources, academic development, personal development, and entertainment or recreational; the extent of media and information sources utilized; and the level of competencies of media and information literacy, specifically the access to media and information resources, evaluation of media and information resources, and use of media and information resources. The moderating variable is the library users of the Baguio City Public Library which evaluates their media and information literacy competencies in the dependent variables. The result of this may propose a library MIL program for the community.

Library Resources

Mondal (2022) pointed out that public libraries are used to provide library resources of information and media to fulfill the needs of the community for education development, private development, and recreation and leisure.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram showing the relationship of concepts used in the study

Generally, they play a pivotal role in the development and preservation of a democratic society. In order to accomplish this, individuals need to have access to a wide range of information, opinions, and ideas. Ikenwe and Adegbilero-Iwari (2014) mentioned that the library is active in the processing, developing collection, processing, archiving, and dissemination of scholarly and documented information for the reason of studying, reading, and consultation. These activities are collectively referred to as library and information services. Furthermore, a

library may provide library resources by acquiring, making relevant information, and organizing resources to make it available to everyone.

There are two types of library resources: print and non-print. Books, journals, theses, and newspapers are some of the print materials and are classified as information sources. CD-ROM, VCD, e-books, and online journals are some of the non-print materials, classified as media resources. Library resources also include personnel, facilities, and equipment.

The types of library resources that will be used are determined by what the library user needs and who the library users are. The library's budgetary allocation will also determine how well it can meet the needs of its library users. According to Iwhiwhu and Okorodudu (2012), the public libraries have been established to provide materials, providing a means of communicating experiences and ideas between people and making them accessible and freely available to the community that it serves. Public libraries are local centers of knowledge and information that make all kinds of information readily available to the public. It is funded, supported, and established by the government, either through a local, regional or national budget or subsidized by private sectors. It supports access to knowledge, information, and works of imagination through the effort of public libraries in providing a range of services and resources. The availability of library resources may have impact on how individuals use the library and the unavailability of library resources needed may lead to dissatisfaction among library users.

Media Resources

The purpose of the different media resources is to communicate, inform, entertain, and advertise a product or service to reach an audience. Moreover, media sources have different formats that aim to target a wider audience across different countries. According to Pantograph (2020), media are categorized into four; broadcast media, print media, Out-of-Home media, or OOH, the internet. Print media encompasses to printed materials, such as newspapers, magazines, books, and pamphlets that contain words and images. Broadcast media eases information transmitted with the aid of one of numerous mass communication channels, like radio, television, and telephone. New media or the internet uses the most recent of digital technologies and newest means of communication. The new media is the primary means of gaining information in a short amount of time. It is a convenient and attractive two-way communication where the users may remain engaged and produce information. Blogs, social media, online articles, online videos, and online streaming are some examples of broadcast media. Out-of-home media, or OOH, is media that reaches the crowd when they are not at home, like billboards, posters, wallscapes, and transit advertisements.

The use of evolving technology in learning, teaching, and research has created challenges and also opportunities for the management of media collections and services in university libraries or academic libraries and community colleges (ACRL, 2018). Librarians and information managers should

be attentive and maintain keeping up with the evolving trends that affect the information-providing scene to offer relevant resources that might help with teaching, learning, and researching. Olanlokun (2010) stated that a media resource is a vital tool in the dissemination of information and making information available to the intended users. Utilization of media resources also refers to minimization of obsolescence, maintenance of the resources for proper stocking, and damage through timely disposal. Proper utilization and preservation of media resources in libraries and information centers will provide adequate media resources that are up-to-date, sustainable, and effective. Hicks (2009) stated that media resources play a vital role in information generation, processing, and dissemination. Thus, media resources like microfilm, sound cassettes, video cassettes, slides, film projectors, CDs, DVDs, Memos, photographs, tape recorders, etc. are very essential in information service provision.

Information Resources

Information is a powerful tool and an important factor in decision-making. One must know numerous sources to gain reliable, timely, relevant, and valuable. We use information for learning, recreation, researching, being updated on current events, exploring innovations, and understanding what is happening around the world.

The University of Minnesota Library (2022) explains the three types of information sources. These are primary, secondary, and tertiary materials and are

classified according to their originality and proximity. Primary sources have no commentary or interpretation. These documents describe events or evidence as they first occurred. Primary sources include original materials that are the basis for other research which are presented for the first time and new discoveries are also displayed. Scholarly journal articles, theses, dissertations, government reports, correspondence, symposia and conference proceedings, autobiographies, interviews, speeches, and diaries are some examples of this classification. Secondary sources analyze or restate, interpret, reorganize, explain, and provide added value to primary sources. Some of the secondary sources are textbooks, books, articles that interpret research works, edited works, biographies, literary criticism, commentaries, and reviews of law and legislation. Tertiary source refers to abstracts, indexes, compilations, organization, and digestions of other sources. The author is usually not credited in tertiary sources. Tertiary sources include encyclopedias, dictionaries, and bibliographies, though these three sources may be considered secondary sources. Others are handbooks, manuals, guidebooks, directories, indexes and abstracts. However, tertiary sources may also include textbooks and reference materials with the primary purpose of listing, summarizing, or repackaging information.

Understanding the different types of information sources allows an individual to forecast the sources; use their use and context. In evaluating the relevance and validity of the information need.

Searching for information is an essential stage for young people to determine what to study and to avoid dropping out of school (Debora, Rodriguez, and Muñiz, et. al. 2011). Their study determined the most used and essential sources of information for students amid the process of deciding on university courses. The study revealed that family plays an important role in deciding which courses to take in college, followed by the World Wide Web, school activities, and career guidance. Students in mixed schools and private use information sources more and they highly value them more than the students in state schools and students who study science branches of bachelor arts and make the most use of the information sources value them the highest.

The study by Echezona, Okafor, and Ukwoma (2011) revealed that postgraduate library and information science students at the University of Nigeria consult and mostly use journals in their research work. Even faculty members at the University of Peshawar in Pakistan found that scholarly journals were the most widely used (Ismail, Muhammad and Khan, Asad, 2021). While faculty members at Vardhaman College of Engineering in South India revealed that electronic journals placed second to textbooks as the most used information sources (Palikiti, Srinivasulu and Srinivasulu, 2018).

In the field of medicine, finding reliable and relevant information sources is vital especially when dealing with health and life. The study by Litzkendorf, Frank, Babac, et al. (2020) revealed that numerous information sources including

the internet, doctors, and self-help organizations have been demonstrated as significant access channels for patients living with a rare disease together with their families. The internet was regarded as the most important and widespread source of initial information by participants. Online searches are viewed by patients as a quick and practical way to search for information, even though they have difficulty dealing with information obtained online.

The study by Baker, Marzouqa, Yaghi, et. al. (2021) gives a perception of the information sources used, preferred, and trusted by students at the Palestinian University. In the early stages of the COVID-19 pandemic, a cross-sectional study was conducted to evaluate their practices, knowledge, and attitudes. According to the study, the World Health Organization (WHO) was the most trusted information source used by students, followed by the Palestinian Ministry of Health (MoH) and healthcare professionals, while, social media was the most frequently used source of information.

Purpose of Utilization

The main goal of the public library is to provide information resources and library services in a diversity of media. This is to meet the needs of every individual and group of people for information, education, and personal development, in addition to recreation and leisure. Furthermore, public libraries play a vital role in the development preservation of a democratic society by

offering individuals to have access to a diverse range of knowledge opinions, and ideas (Koontz and Gubbin, 2010).

The goal of public libraries is to provide quality library services in the community since they cater to diverse library users. The availability of information sources and media resources is a key factor in recognizing the value of any library. The information must be readily available in sufficient quantities, reliable, accurate, up-to-date, and relevant to the user's needs and requirements. The library should consider excellent facilities and innovative library programs and services to increase patronage. Also, utilization could be enhanced through good staff-user relationships (Okwor, 2015). Furthermore, the availability of library resources affects how often the library is utilized. It should be available to its library users for their personal purposes to boost the patronage of library. Likewise, the availability of information sources could advocate the presence of an information center or library (Nwachukwu, et. al. 2014).

Utilization primarily aims to meet the informational needs of users (Ezekwe, 2019). Library users use the library for a wide range of reasons, including studying a lesson, reviewing for incoming examinations and board exams, researching, using the internet, and borrowing books. Furthermore, any library's success is based on the library resources it has and how well it utilizes those library resources (Aladeniyi and Owokole, 2018). Libraries need to have an adequate and wide range of library resources that library users can utilize. Having

access to these library resources is not enough, but library users must utilize them to benefit from them.

Academic Development. The library is an essential aspect of the educational system that supports learning generally. According to Koontz and Gubbin (2010), public libraries perform core functions, including providing access to knowledge in printed materials and other forms like internet sources and multimedia that will support formal and informal education.

The public has also the role to provide the educational needs of library users in the community. There are studies showed that one of the purposes is academic or educational needs. The study by Ani, Ekeh, Ezemoyih, et. al. (2022) revealed that students primarily consult books and reference materials in the library for academic use. According to Pandeewaran, Chellappandi and Bhattacharya (2021) reading newspapers and learning through books are the top purposes of the respondents in utilizing the public library. Furthermore, the other purpose of the students was studying, reading books, using computer databases for searching information, browsing reference materials, and also reading the books that they brought (Evalle, 2017). Similar to the study by Jamil, Shah, and Tariq (2013) students mostly visit libraries for reading books to pass the time.

The study by Bhatti (2013) showed that library users mostly came to the library every week for the reason of reading books, preparing for examinations, and making class assignments, and that they prefer books available at the library

than reference material, theses, and journals. While the study of Ikenwe and Adegbilero-Iwari (2014) revealed that the majority of library users visited the library in preparation for examination while some of the library users are to obtain general information for their particular purposes.

In the Philippines, the most common reasons for visiting public libraries are related to academic and school needs and it has perceived that students are top users of the public library (National Library of the Philippines, 2019). Likewise, the study by Bernardo (2016) revealed that school-related research is the most common reason for seeking information at the Baguio City Library.

Personal Development. For human development to occur, it is imperative to provide opportunities for the development of creative skills and the pursuit of new interests. In order to accomplish this, it is important for people to have access to knowledge and works of imagination. Good thing it's there a public library that provides access, in many forms of media, to an omnipresent and diverse wealth of knowledge and imaginative achievement that individuals cannot obtain on their own. Offering access to a major collection of the world's knowledge and literature, incorporating the community's local literature is an invaluable contribution vital function of the public library. Access to knowledge and works of the imagination are vital contributions to personal education and worthwhile recreational activity (Koontz and Gubbin, 2010).

There are several studies that proved that personal development is one of

the important purposes to visit the library. For instance, the study by Bala and Poolpandianshows (2019) and Kamruzzaman, Hasan, and Islam (2019) revealed that the second purpose of the respondents in visiting the library is to update themselves about current information or keep them up-to-date on current events. It helps them stay informed about a wide range of topics and make more informed decisions.

Entertainment or Recreation. The public library is not only for academic, education, and personal development but also play a significant role in people's lives by providing entertainment and recreational opportunities. Reading newspaper and magazines, playing board games, attending to storytelling, reading fiction books, and gaming are some of the entertainment and recreational activities at the library. Public libraries have a healthy and positive impact on people's leisure time. The benefits of having public libraries include relaxation, enhance critical thinking, alleviating boredom, develop well-being, and create socialization. Alvarez (2017) mentioned that tabletop gaming supports young people in forming healthy habits, building comprehension skills, and becoming more active in the library. Besides, digital games can also be incorporated into library programs to develop literacy skills.

It is observed in the study by Bala and Poolpandianshows (2019), that reading the newspaper is the top purpose of the respondents. According to Kamruzzaman, Hasan, and Islam (2019), the majority of library users visit the

library to use and read newspapers and magazines. It is also revealed that in the study by Bala, and Shahnaz (2022), that the main reason of the respondent's purpose in visiting the public library is reading newspapers. While the study by Patil, Rohit, Kumbar, and Kamble (2019), reading newspapers and magazines placed the second purpose of library users for visiting the public library.

However, some concerns came up in the utilization of library resources. The study by Jamil, Shah, and Tariq (2013) revealed that despite that students and teachers expressed a desire to use libraries, but it was observed that libraries are underutilized. The reasons are lack of material resources and human resources. Besides, professional training is needed for the library staff, as well as collection development and acquisition of library resources. In addition, virtual library linkages between national libraries and international libraries need to be addressed and proper funding and utilization of budget is required to enhance efficiency. The improvement and provision of library services can improve the utilization and relevance of libraries.

In addition, the unavailability of information resources may lead to dissatisfaction among library users. The study by Tiemo and Ateboh (2016) revealed that library users felt dissatisfied with the lack of reference materials offered in their respective subject areas, including national journals and international journals because they were out of date. Likewise, the respondents of public libraries were dissatisfied with the information resources and library

services provided as a result of insufficient attention provided to the library. (Abdullahi and Aliyu, 2019). Therefore, to increase utilization, libraries must acquire updated information sources both print and non-print, and the creation of library collection development. Also, the innovation of library services and programs may have a great and encouraging impact to attract users.

Extent of Media and Information Resources Utilized

The utilization of the information sources and media resources depends on the library user's needs, purpose, and preferred format. Utilization refers to the total use of library resources and library facilities for some genuine purposes considering the guidance of library staff (Ani, Ekeh, Ezemoyih, et. al., 2022).

Preferred formats and the availability of information sources and media resources are also a concern in delivering the information needs of library users. MacKay, Mills, and Brent (2012) stated that the information was highly structured. Most students use printed materials like books, and journals from their library to complete their tasks and sometimes, they get assistance from librarians. However, everything has changed radically with the internet and online resources. Shrestha (2008) also mentioned that students today are more likely to place information that is quick to find due to the fast-paced world. Many students limit their search strategies to electronic resources, selecting format over substance and convenience over accuracy. They are relying on the World Wide Web as a

generally sole research strategy has influenced the quality and rigorousness of students' projects. This has reduced students' perception of more common bibliographical databases and print resources in their academic library.

The rapid growth of information technology affects the way we access the information we need. The 21st century is surrounded by developments in technology, the internet, and media. Today, with the use of the computer and the internet, information is just a click away. Cellphones are not only for communication but also use as a mini-computer. With the innovation of cell phones and the introduction of Wi-Fi, information has become readily available.

Several studies were undertaken to determine what library resources do library users prefer to utilize and the reasons behind their choices. The aim is to compare the utilization of the different formats of information sources.

Students in the universities revealed that they made great use of e-resources in Tezpur University (Saikia and Gohain, 2013). Also, it was found that there is a high utilization of journals in Muhimbili University (Ruzegea and Msonde, 2021). A study by Kumah (2015) discovered that the internet was the most popular source of information used by teachers, research scholars, and students. However, it is not common for students to avoid the library when it comes to fulfilling their informational needs. Both the library and the internet are used by them. Furthermore, books, ready reference collections, magazines, and newspapers are still utilized by most students and library users (Evalle, 2017;

Nagaraju and Cuaycong, 2015; Rayat, 2014).

Another study by Salubi, Ondari-Okemwa, and Nekhwevha (2018) revealed that the widely utilized library resource by students is Wi-Fi with e-books, while e-journals were found to be the least utilized. It was also recorded by the e-librarians that students who have access to electronic databases prefer print information resources over electronic databases.

The study by Khan (2012) revealed that a good number of faculty members and research scholars use journals and scholarly journals like emeraldinsight.com and sciencedirect.com for obtaining the information they need. In contrast, students prefer general books but journals as second choice for obtaining the information they need.

The study by Ezeala (2022) revealed the common library resources used by faculty staff and students. Majority of faculty staff use textbooks and reference materials while students were less likely to use them though there are few collections in the library. Besides, most of the students use books, newspapers, theses and dissertations, journals, Filipiniana materials, and international abstracts, as they are readily accessible, while eLibrary USA and ProQuest are not widely used because they are inaccessible (Cuaycong, 2015). The study by Kamruzzaman, Hasan, and Islam (2019) showed that the majority of the respondents preferred newspapers and placed at first rank, followed by online resources.

The various studies mentioned earlier show that in general there is no definite type of information and media sources that are most used and that both print and non-print format are being utilized. The top resources utilized depend on the library they serve.

Level of Media and Information Competencies

Competency is a skill, ability, aptitude, area of knowledge, or behavioral characteristic that is linked with high performance (British University of Columbia, 2022). It is of the utmost importance to guarantee that all individuals have the competences, skills, knowledge, and attitudes to succeed across all stages of the information and media life cycle, and to assist people in meeting their requirements, flourishing, and improving the quality of their lives (Moeller, Joseph, Lau, and Carbo, 2010).

Information literacy competency is a combination of skills, ability, knowledge, and attitudes in the direction of understanding and recognizing what, why, and when information is needed, how manage and apply it, where to access it, how to evaluate, and how to synthesize, and how to communicate it and use it legally and ethically (Anunobi and Udem, 2014). Moreover, UNESCO (2013) stresses that being literate involves being able to interpret and make informed decisions as skillful consumers of information and media texts.

Likewise, the MIL competencies will serve as a guide that will prepare the

community to be competent individuals. This is a realistic result of UNESCO's institutional and individual partners' MIL efforts under the Global MIL Assessment Framework. (UNESCO, 2013). The three MIL competencies are categorized into three fundamental components: access, evaluation, and use or creation. The three MIL components are broad assertions that are directly related to MIL subject matters as illustrated in Figure 2.

The first component is access and the subject matters are articulation or definition, search or location, access, and retrieval. The second component is evaluation and subject matters are understanding, assessment, evaluation, and organization. The third component is creation or use and the subject matters are creation, communication, participation, and monitoring.

Figure 2. MIL broad components associated with the MIL subject matters

There are various academic journals and research studies from around the world highlight concerns about MIL competencies and skills which discussed the three components and the competencies of the respondents. Also, possible explanations were brought out to address the outcomes of the conducted research.

The results of a study by Somabut, Sumalee, and Tuamsuk (2016) conducted in Thailand revealed that integrating MIL into the learning environment can help students to enhance their level of MIL competencies. Through constructivist learning, students learned how to access, evaluate and use media and information, in addition to gaining experience with communication skills, creative and critical thinking. The results of the study also offer significant encouragement and support for Thailand teachers to integrate constructivist learning and MIL initiatives in the school to enhance teaching and learning in the twenty-first century.

In the Philippines, a study by Rusiana and Naporata (2021) showed that the level of competencies in MIL of high school students was above average and interpreted as good from access, evaluation, and use of media and information sources. Since the students possess a good level in the three main competencies, it is generally suggested that education practitioners and librarians must make careful consideration to factors that influence students' ability to improve their MIL competencies.

Labangon and Zabala (2018) conducted a study about MIL

implementation in the Philippines that was presented at the 17th Conference of Southeast Asian Libraries. The study revealed that the instructors as respondents were not exposed to MIL training because of the absence of such training sessions. This adds to the concern on how well they impart instruction to their students as a result. School libraries appeared to be an active resource for MIL instructors, while public libraries were less visible. Barangay reading centers were not mentioned as supplementary facilities for MIL instruction. The integration of MIL in libraries helps instructors and even students learn the competencies aside from what they learn from formal education in their schools. Furthermore, it is necessary to conduct more extensive research to track and describe the development of MIL in the Philippines. Even though the number of respondents was limited and only four regions of the nation's total were represented in the data nonetheless the research has gathered significant results. The implementation of MIL in those regions must not be applied nationally.

Moreover, the presence of MIL library programs and services creates a literate society or community. A study conducted by Dela Cruz (2016) in Ateneo de Manila assessed the effectiveness of the Media Instruction Program (MIP) to grade school. The school library created the media information modules and it was observed that there is an increased and improved significance of grade five students coming after they were exposed to the MIP. The results of the assessment were noticeable in their test scores. Also, the study revealed that school librarians

from Ateneo de Manila played an essential role in exposing and training pupils to make the most of library resources, and its programs and services which lead to enhancing their MIL skills.

Access to Media and Information. From UNESCO's MIL framework (2013), access is the first MIL component which is considered as having the ability to use appropriate technology to access, retrieve, and store information and media contents. To meet this requirement, one must be able to identify the need for information, knowledge, and media content, and be able to identify relevant information and media from a wide range of sources and formats, including digital, print, visual, and audio. Retrieval may be done using physical or electronic storage and may come from any source, including libraries, personal files, and museums.

Access to MIL covers the following competencies: identify and articulate the scope, role, and nature content of information and media through a wide range of resources; search and locate the needed information and media; access effectively and ethically the needed information and media which includes the information and media providers; and, retrieve information and media using a range of methods and tools.

There were studies that described the level of competencies of media and information literacy specifically in access to MIL. In Iran, the study by Ashrafi, et. al. (2014) showed that students lacked skills in generating the research subject,

defining the research subject, also refining the research subject. With the results of the study, he stressed that students and educators should ought to devote special attention to aspects affecting the development of competencies in MIL as the main ability in using printed and electronic media.

The study Tibaldo (2021) revealed that Language and Communication students have an overall intermediate competency level or translated to average skills in access to information and media, and information resources. This shows that they have an above-average level of knowledge and abilities gained from MIL practice and training, but it also suggests that they have certain gaps in specific areas of skills.

While the study of Ilogho and Nkiko (2014) discovered that the majority of the respondents lacked knowledge about information literacy. It also demonstrated that the respondents lacked knowledge in recognizing multiple information sources, and the numerous information literacy programs offered by the institutions. Besides, respondents lacked hands-on experience. Moreover, it indicates that information literacy skills should be included in secondary and higher education curricula to assist students to develop their information literacy skills. As a result, there is a need for improved and ongoing library user education aimed at empowering students to become effectively acquainted with information sources. A mutual partnership between librarians and educators enables an integrated form of information literacy advocacy to assist students' learning.

Furthermore, the study found that strong information literacy skills are essential for knowledge acquisition in today's digital age.

In addition, the existence of media or digital literacy programs in libraries has a significant impact to enhance the skills of every library user. A study by Horrigan (2016) revealed that a large majority of Americans believe that libraries have to provide programs to educate digital skills and assist users in learning how to use new creative technology.

Evaluation of Media and Information. The second component of MIL is evaluation, which UNESCO (2013) defined as the ability to critically analyze, understand, and evaluate information and media content. Some skills are assessing the accuracy, relevance, and reliability of information and media contents and comparing facts.

Recent studies discussed the level of competencies in the evaluation of media and information. The study by Tibaldo (2021) showed that Language and Communication students have an intermediate level of skills but they can still be upgraded through continuous training. Advanced level of competencies will be achieved because it's a continuing exist that can progressively enhance.

The study by Inayatillah (2018) found that journalist students majoring in Indonesian literature Universitas Negeri Surabaya lacked MIL skills in the preliminary observations. Their skills are lacking in terms of identifying

information needs, accessing information, locating information needs, criticizing information, and formulating information obtain.

Compared to the study of Anunobi and Udem (2015) revealed that the postgraduate students majoring in library and information science in Nigerian Universities possessed a moderate level of information literacy skills. They can understand why and when they need information, where to find the information they need, how they evaluate information, and how they use and communicate the information in legal and ethical ways.

Use of Media and Information. The third component of MIL is use or creation. It encompasses the ability to use information, media content, and general knowledge ethically and legally, and communicate with others (UNESCO, 2013).

Previous studies have revealed the level of competencies in the use of media and information. The study by Tibaldo (2021) stated that students have intermediate skills in the use of information and media content. Overall, his study revealed that all MIL major competencies of students were intermediate.

According to the findings of Enakrire and Mothiba (2020), it found that library users in Saulsville Public Library had a minimal level of competencies in information literacy despite that the library users were provided with library orientation and utilized library resources in the library. It was pointed out that to enhance library users' level of competencies; it suggested that it needs to have interactive information literacy training in public libraries and school programs.

Library Users

The IFLA/UNESCO (2001) manifesto specifies the local gateway that the public library is the local gateway of information, making all kinds of knowledge and information readily available to its library users. The public library's services are made available to everyone equally, regardless of race, gender, religion, language, nationality, or social standing. Likewise, this is further supported by the study of Maurya (2016) which stated that public libraries play a great role in the development of society. They were created to provide continuing education, recreation opportunities, economic development, and cultural engagement regardless of age, cast, sex, and creed.

Public libraries provide the information, education, and social needs of the community and cater to a diverse group of users. Iwhiwhu and Okorodudu (2012) stated that people from all walks of life use public library resources, services, and facilities. These library users include students, pupils, scholars, teachers, scientists, government officials, business executives, and even dropouts. Numerous people come to public libraries to satisfy their needs and desires or to obtain information sources for particular purposes.

A study by Chinnasamy and Nachimuthu (2022) revealed that the largest library users of public libraries in Chennai is the group of aged less than twenty, followed by aged twenty-one to thirty. Most of this age group belongs with the status of students. Similar to the study by Iwhiwhu and Okorodudu (2012),

Kamruzzaman, Hasan, and Islam (2019), and Aslam and Sonker (2018) that the majority of library users in public libraries were students or aged twenty-one to twenty-five followed by aged twenty-six to thirty-five.

It is related to a study by Horrigan (2016) discovered that the majority of the library users who visited public libraries were aged sixteen years and older or young adults. The significant reason why young ones visit public libraries is that there are available resources they need and play in helping them decide the information they can use and trust.

Based on the studies mentioned, it was discovered that students continue to visit public libraries even when they have access to libraries at their respective schools, colleges, and universities. This indicates that public libraries play a vital role in supporting the educational needs of students.

To increase adults to senior users of public libraries, public libraries should create or develop library programs and services for them. For instance, a study by Wilhelm and Jones (2019) discovered that there was an increase in adult attendance in the usage of the library when they introduce informal science, technology, engineering, and math (STEM) programs for them. Also, the goal of their library program is to encourage lifelong learning and civic engagement and strengthen ties to both the local university and the community.

Student. One of the library users of the Baguio City Public Library belongs to group of a students. A student is a person who is studying at a

university or college (Collins, 2022). They are currently enrolled in their respective school, university, or college. Even though their school has a library, students come to the public library to do their research and assignments.

Employed. A group of employed library users also use public libraries to satisfy their thirst for wisdom or to obtain media and information resources for their work-related needs. Likewise, every expert individuals, professionals, and skilled persons requires and needs up-to-date knowledge in his chosen profession or career, and information relating to having better jobs (Anyira, 2011). Employed refer to people with jobs working for a company or another person (Cambridge Dictionary, 2022). Group of the employed library users includes public employees, private employees, and self-employed.

Unemployed. People from all walks of life use the public library. These library users include the unemployed, particularly senior citizens, parents, homemakers, out-of-school youth, and college graduates reviewing for their incoming board or licensure examinations. According to Oxford (2022), unemployed means a person without a job but is available to work.

Statement of the Problem

The purpose of this study is to assess the media and information literacy competencies of the diverse library users of Baguio City Public Library. Furthermore, this study provided a reliable point of reference for the development

of public services.

Specifically, the study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What are the different purposes of library users in utilizing the media and information resources?

2. What is the extent of the utilization of media and information resources by library users?

3. What is the level of competencies of media and information skills of library users specifically the following?

- a. Access to media and information
- b. Evaluation of media and information
- c. Use of media and information

Hypothesis of the Study

There is a significant difference in the level of media and information literacy competencies among the employed, unemployed and the student library users.

METHODOLOGY

This chapter contains a detailed description of the research design, population and locale of the study, data collection instrument, data collection procedure, and treatment of the data.

Research Design

The study employs a descriptive method of research. Descriptive research determine and report things. Descriptive research, then, is a type of study that occurs naturally, having no control toward the condition along with the environment, and is limited to measuring what is already existent. (Arifin, 2016). The study used a survey questionnaire serving as the primary tool for gathering data. It aims to determine the profile of the library users, the purpose of utilization of media and information sources by library users, the extent of media and information resources utilized by library users, and the level of media and information literacy competencies of library users.

Population and Locale of the Study

The respondents of this research were the diverse library users of Baguio City Public Library. A sampling design was used and the survey was conducted during the library hours of Baguio City Public Library (BCPL). The survey questionnaires were circulated for one month. Three hundred ninety-five

questionnaires have been distributed to the public library users. Out of three hundred ninety-five questionnaires, three hundred seventy-four usable response sheets were received. Table 1 shows the breakdown of the library users of the Baguio City Public Library who serves as respondents and figure 3 shows the location of the study.

Table 1. Profile of respondents

GROUP OF USERS	NUMBER	PERCENTAGE
Students		
High School	50	13.37%
College	151	40.38%
Graduate School	21	5.61%
Total	222	59.36%
Employed		
Public Sector	15	4.01%
Private Sector	14	3.74%
Self-employed	17	4.55%
Total	46	12.30%
Unemployed		
College Graduate	104	27.80%
Senior Citizens	1	0.27%
Out-of-school Youth	1	0.27%
Total	106	28.34%
Total	374	100%

Figure 3. Location map of Baguio City Public Library

Data Collection Instrument

The main instrument of the study was a survey questionnaire (Appendix A) with a cover letter for the respondents (Appendix B). Part I, Part II, and Part III were self-formulated questionnaires, and a four-Likert scale was used. Part IV was adapted with changes, from a five-Likert to a four-Likert scale which was applicable to use in this study. The questionnaire's parts were all of the checklist types.

Part I consisted of the profile of the respondents like educational attainment and career status. Part II gathered the purpose of using the media and information resources in the public library. Part III is a list of media and information resources found at the public library used by library users. Part IV assessed the library users' level of competencies. This part of the questionnaire was adapted from the study of Ahmad titled Information Literacy Skills of Researchers published in 2017. The study is available online at Research Gate, a repository for open access to research.

To ensure the accuracy and reliability of the questionnaire, a pre-test was conducted at Baguio City Public Library from December 19 to December 23, 2022. Respondents were those who actually made use of the public library at the time. Pre-test respondents are excluded from the testing period to avoid duplication. Cronbach's alpha (Appendix D) was used to determine the internal consistency of the survey questionnaire. Based on the pre-test results, the instrument is reliable. The cronbach's alpha of the different purposes of library users in utilization of media and information resources is zero point eighty-three (0.83); the extent of the utilization of media and information resources by library users is zero point ninety-four (0.94); and the level of competencies of media and information skills of library users is zero point ninety-four (0.95). In general, the higher the cronbach's alpha, the more reliable the instrument is. The cut-off of reliability is usually at zero point seventy (0.70). Below 0.70, it is not reliable.

Data Collection Procedure

To formally access the respondents and conduct the administration of survey questionnaire, a communication letter (Appendix C) was sent to the head of the office of the Baguio City Public Library (BCPL). Upon approval, the researcher personally approached the library users of the BCPL to answer the survey questionnaire promptly regarding their media and information literacy competencies. To prevent duplication, respondents were also asked if they had already completed the survey questionnaire. It was then collected after the library user answered the survey questionnaire. The researcher had also the chance to talk to the respondents for additional inputs, clarifications, and further insights about media and information literacy. In order to gather more respondents, a month of data collection was conducted. This was done to ensure that the responses were more statistically significant, as a larger sample size would provide a more accurate representation of the target population. Data gathering was conducted from January 26, 2023, to February 24, 2023.

Treatment of Data

The data gathered from the survey questionnaire were tallied, classified, and tabulated for analysis and interpretation using descriptive statistics. Frequency count and percentage were analyzed and the data were interpreted on purposes of utilization of media and information resources, the extent of

utilization of the media and information resources, and the level of competencies of library users. The mean was also used to determine the purpose of utilization, the extent of utilization, and the level of competencies. In interpreting the mean for the descriptive statistics, a four-point Likert scale was used with varying descriptions depending on the subject of the questions. In interpreting the mean for descriptive statistics, the following scale was used in each table.

Table 2 represents the purpose of utilization of media and information resources by library users at the BCPL. Library users use the public library for academic development, personal development, and for entertainment or recreation. Descriptive interpretations were always, sometimes, rarely, and never.

Table 2. Scale on the purpose in the utilization of media and information resources by library users at the Baguio City Public Library

SCALE	WEIGHTED MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE INTERPRETATION	EXPLANATION
4	3.26-4.00	Always	I spend my time (purpose) five to six times a week in the library.
3	2.51-3.25	Sometimes	I spend my time (purpose) three to four times a week in the library.
2	1.76-2.50	Rarely	I spend my time (purpose) one to two times a week in the library.
1	1.00-1.75	Never	I never spend my time (purpose) in the library

Table 3 displays the extent of media and information resources utilized

by the library users at the BCPL. These are categorized into two: print materials and non-print materials. Print materials comprised six media and library resources while non-print materials had eleven media and information resources. These resources are available at BCPL. It was also determined how often they used the available media and information resources found at the public library. There are four descriptions used: always utilized, sometimes utilized, rarely utilized, and not utilized.

Table 3. Scale on the extent of media and information resources utilized by the library users at Baguio City Public Library

SCALE	WEIGHTED MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE INTERPRETATION	EXPLANATION
4	3.26-4.00	Always Utilized	At all times I use the media and information resources.
3	2.51-3.25	Sometimes Utilized	I usually make use of the media and information resources.
2	1.76-2.50	Rarely Utilized	I occasionally make use of the media and information resources.
1	1.00-1.75	Not/Never Utilized	I don't use the media and information resources at all.

Table 4 indicated the level of MIL competencies of library users at Baguio City Public Library. Media and information literacy competencies were assessed

in terms of access to media and information resources, evaluation of media and information resources, and use of media and information resources.

Table 4. Scale on the level of media and information competencies of the library users at Baguio City Public Library

SCALE	WEIGHTED MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE INTERPRETATION	EXPLANATION
4	3.26-4.00	Advance	I am extremely confident in my ability and skills to access, evaluate, and make use of media and information resources.
3	2.51-3.25	Intermediate	I am moderately confident in my ability and skills to access, evaluate, and make use of media and information resources.
2	1.76-2.50	Basic	I am somewhat confident in my ability and skills to access, evaluate, and make use of media and information resources.
1	1.00-1.75	Poor	I am not confident in my ability and skills to access, evaluate, and make use of media and information resources.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter reveals the presentation and interpretation of the data gathered from the students, unemployed, and employed users of Baguio City Public Library. It presents a discussion of the findings regarding the frequency of different purposes of library users in utilization of media and information resources, the extent of utilization of media and information resources by library users, and the level of competency of media and information skills of library users.

Different Purposes of Library Users in Utilizing Media and Information Resources

There is no doubt that public libraries have played a pivotal role in modern society until now. People from all walks of life like students, employed, and unemployed go to public libraries for different purposes. The results of this study found the primary reasons why they visit the public library. Table 5 shows the ranking of the frequency of different purposes of library users in the utilization of media and information resources. Results show that library users mainly use media and information resources for academic development purposes (mean = 2.53, sometimes). This is followed by both personal development (mean = 2.47, rarely) and entertainment/recreation purposes (mean = 1.73, rarely).

Given that the majority of respondents are students (59.36%), it naturally

Table 5. Purposes of library users in utilizing media and information resources

PURPOSE	MEAN	FREQUENCY
1. Academic development	2.53	Sometimes
2. Personal development	2.47	Rarely
3. Entertainment/recreation	1.73	Rarely

Mean range: 3.50-4.00=Always; 2.50-3.49=Sometimes; 1.50-2.49=Rarely; 1.00-1.49=Never

follows that the purpose is academic development. In addition, some of the employed group is also pursuing a master's degree. The leading purpose of the student is likely to gain insight into how they can best improve their education. This could involve gathering information about the current state of their learning environment and accessing library resources for their academic requirement. Students are doing their best to achieve high performance in their educational goals. They are increasing their knowledge and taking advantage of library resources.

It implies that library users recognize the public library's educational value which provides them with library resources that meets their educational needs, proving the importance of public libraries in the education sector. It is suggested that the public library serves students' academic needs as a source of information and a space for learning.

As mentioned by Gados and Lascano (2021) during the student's academic journey; some of the students' academic requirements during the course of their schooling are in line with manuscript writing and research. This is why

students need to find all relevant information sources that tackle the scope they need to do. Furthermore, this study supports the results of Bernardo (2016), which found that school-related research and tasks were the top reason for utilizing the city library, and based on the study by Pablo (2013) respondents perceived the educational role as the most important. Further, this is proven by the research of the National Library of the Philippines (2019) that the main purposes for visiting public libraries were related to school requirements and the academic needs of students.

Along with Academic Development

Table 6 presents the specific purposes of library users in using library resources at the public library along with academic development. It shows library users come to the library to study or review their lessons for incoming periodic examinations (mean = 2.91, sometimes) and to read references that supplement their studies or school requirements (mean = 2.58, sometimes). Other purposes are rare (mean = 2.37 and 2.39).

Library users utilize the public library because it offers a conducive and comfortable atmosphere to focus on their studies and review their lessons. They are likely to come to the public library to prepare for examinations. It might make them confident they will get better grades if they are fully prepared. Additionally, books from their school are not enough to supplement their studies and school requirements. With the ever-increasing cost of textbooks, library users find it

Table 6. Purposes of library users in utilizing media and information resources along academic development

ACADEMIC DEVELOPMENT	S	U	E	WEIGHTED MEAN	FREQUENCY
1. To study or review my lessons for incoming quarterly/semestral examination.	2.85	3.18	2.53	2.91	Sometimes
2. To consult books and obtain other relevant information for my research or assignment.	2.39	2.19	2.71	2.37	Rarely
3. To answer my online activities and do my school requirement.	2.53	2.17	2.23	2.39	Rarely
4. To read references that will supplement my studies or school requirement.	2.62	2.41	2.80	2.58	Sometimes
5. To access online resources.	2.41	2.37	2.32	2.39	Rarely
TOTAL WEIGHTED MEAN	2.56	2.47	2.52	2.53	SOMETIMES

Group of Users: S=Student, U=Unemployed, E=Employed

Mean range: 3.50-4.00=Always; 2.50-3.49=Sometimes; 1.50-2.49=Rarely; 1.00-1.49=Never

convenient to access relevant library resources for their studies and maximize the use of free library resources provided by the public library.

It denotes that library users see the public library as a learning environment. They perceive that the public library is a conducive place to study or review lessons for upcoming periodic examinations. They recognize public libraries as sources of media and information to fulfill school requirements in addition to school and academic libraries.

It was pointed out by Howlett, Partridge and Belov (2017) that public libraries within the community provide valuable learning resources to support university students with their learning requirements and needs. The study recognized the impact of working with public libraries to provide and extend learning support to students presents a great opportunity for universities in regional and rural communities. In addition, a study by Clark and Hawkins (2011) revealed the most common reasons why young people use public libraries is because public libraries have interesting reading materials, which helps them do better at school.

Along with Personal Development

Following the academic development purpose is personal development. The public library is not only for borrowing books, but also for finding information related to careers, hobbies, or interests, which can help foster personal growth. Anchoring personal development, five possible specific purposes are identified, as shown in Table 7. Most library users use the public library to review for their incoming licensure/board/civil service examination (mean = 2.75, sometimes). The other top personal development purposes are learning new skills through reading (mean = 2.71, sometimes) and exploring available library references, and enhancing knowledge (mean = 2.63, sometimes).

Given that the second population of respondents is unemployed (28.34%), and the majority of college graduates (27.80%), it naturally follows that the most

Table 7. Purposes of library users in utilizing media and information resources along personal development

PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT	S	U	E	WEIGHTED MEAN	FREQUENCY
1. To explore the available library references and enhance my knowledge.	2.67	2.40	2.98	2.63	Sometimes
2. To learn new skills through reading.	2.74	2.62	2.78	2.71	Sometimes
3. To review for my incoming licensure/board/civil service examination.	2.37	3.55	2.78	2.75	Sometimes
4. To keep up to date with current events.	2.01	2.19	2.23	2.09	Rarely
5. To read books about inspiration.	2.26	1.85	2.33	2.15	Rarely
TOTAL WEIGHTED MEAN	2.41	2.52	2.62	2.47	RARELY

Group of Users: S=Student, U=Unemployed, E=Employed

Mean range: 3.50-4.00=Always; 2.50-3.49=Sometimes; 1.50-2.49=Rarely; 1.00-1.49=Never

purpose is to review for their incoming licensure/board/civil service examination. College graduates have a variety of goals, but the most common is to prepare for an exam that will help them gain access to their desired careers. This could be a professional certification or a specialized degree in their field of choice. With the right preparation, they can enter the job market with the skills and knowledge necessary to be successful. Other than that, library users use library resources to gain knowledge and skills, discover new hobbies, and obtain insights for career development through the reading of books and accessing online resources and internet.

It is observed that library users slightly perceive the public library as a place for personal development. Also, it indicates that the public library is a study-friendly environment where library users can focus on reviewing due to minimal distractions. Moreover, this suggests that library users consider the public library to have a collection of materials for a wide range of interest which can provide them with knowledge and skills that they can access for free.

Agyekum (2022) mentioned that the library is open to all and a public place to use by people. His study revealed that most library users have great experience with the public library and it has played a positive role in learning, reading, and writing, as well as describing how the public library provides a place for vibrant study. Among others, they avail of library services such as adult literacy education for immigrants and free internet and computer access. Thus, public libraries play an important role not only for academic development but also for personal growth. It was pointed out by Uzomba (2014) that one of the major roles of libraries is to create and enhance a literacy-friendly environment. Among others is to provide equitable and free access to information, and attractive reading materials for everyone.

Along with Entertainment/Recreation

The public library also plays a role in entertainment, recreation, or leisure. They provide access to fiction books, newspapers, magazines, the internet, and television. Also, they host events and activities such as storytelling, arts and

crafts, and talk shows that provide recreational opportunities for everyone. However, entertainment/recreation (total weighted mean = 1.73, rarely) is the least frequent purpose of library users for visiting the public library as presented in Table 8. Based on the results, no statement was interpreted as at least ‘Sometimes’. It is also noticeable that statement 3, to watch television (mean = 1.44) is an interpretation of ‘Never’.

A significant reason for this is the absence of some library programs and activities. In addition, there is not enough space at the public library to fulfill its entertainment role. Though the results are rarely used, they are used to browse the internet for leisure like Facebook and YouTube. The public library does not filter social networking and video-sharing websites. Consequently, library users can

Table 8. Purposes of library users in utilizing media and information resources along entertainment/recreational development

ENTERTAINMENT/ RECREATION	S	U	E	WEIGHTED MEAN	FREQUENCY
1. To read newspapers and magazines.	1.66	1.58	2.09	1.69	Rarely
2. To read fiction books.	2.01	1.52	1.86	1.86	Rarely
3. To watch the television.	1.46	1.39	1.41	1.44	Never
4. To pass leisure time by browsing the internet, connecting to Wi-Fi, and browsing YouTube and Facebook.	2.03	1.78	1.89	1.94	Rarely
TOTAL WEIGHTED MEAN	1.79	1.57	1.81	1.73	RARELY

Group of Users: S=Student, U=Unemployed, E=Employed

Mean range: 3.50-4.00=Always; 2.50-3.49=Sometimes; 1.50-2.49=Rarely; 1.00-1.49=Never

also learn from these websites. YouTube has entertainment as well as educational content. Library users can also learn and update themselves on government agencies' Facebook pages. Facebook pages serve as a tool to promote and provide information regarding the company's products and services of private institutions and government units. Moreover, the public library has a Facebook page to reach the community. It is interesting to note that reading fiction books is also a second purpose of entertainment/recreation. It was observed that fiction books are read more because of the 'book lovers' club in the public library.

Since entertainment/recreation is the least significant purpose, it indicates that the majority of library users do not view the public library as a place for entertainment/recreation. It suggests that the presence of other library recreation activities and further collection and development of media and information resources will increase to fulfill the entertainment role.

As Wyatt, McQuire, and Butt (2015) confirmed, in a market-driven society, there are many opportunities for entertainment. Libraries offer and promote an inclusive learning environment where social capital across different cultural groups and communities is encouraged. In their study, respondents talked about the effectiveness of gaming and gaming days in engaging young adults in the library. The idea is to become proactive in creating an atmosphere of leisure and consumer culture by offering games in the library.

Correspondingly, Christa (2016) stated that there is no doubt that game

programming and the building of game collections have proven beneficial to all kinds of libraries. They can serve as tools for learning, sources of entertainment, and venues for social interaction and group community building.

Extent of Utilization of Media and Information Resources by Library Users

The public library provides access to various media and information resources such as books, theses, dissertations, internet connection, e-books, and computers. Table 9 shows the mean response of the utilization of print and non-print materials by library users. From the results, both print materials (mean = 2.07, rarely) and non-print materials (mean = 1.94, rarely) have equal utilization. The mean scores show that out of the seventeen (17) library resources listed, only the reference books (mean = 2.7) and internet searching/browsing (mean = 2.84) are utilized to the extent of sometimes, the rest of the library resources ranging from between 1.65 to 2.17 mean score and are utilized to the extent of rarely. Even though the extent of utilization of library resources is rare (total weighted mean = 2.01) but the three most utilized media and information resources are internet searching/browsing and reference books followed by theses and dissertations. The least utilized are educational CDs/VCDs.

In this digital world, it is no surprise that library users use the internet as their top media and information resource. The majority of library users maximize the use of the free internet at the public library for academic development,

Table 9. Utilization of print and non-print materials by library users

MEDIA AND INFORMATION RESOURCES	S	U	E	WEIGHTED MEAN	EXTENT
A. Print Materials	2.17	1.78	2.27	2.07	Rarely
1. Reference Books, Books/Textbooks	2.77	2.38	2.96	2.70	Sometimes
2. Newspaper and magazine	1.98	1.72	2.22	1.93	Rarely
3. Globes, Maps	1.91	1.49	2.07	1.8	Rarely
4. Brochure and Pamphlets	1.94	1.59	2.02	1.83	Rarely
5. Theses and Dissertation	2.25	1.88	2.67	2.17	Rarely
6. Fiction Books	2.19	1.64	2.30	2.00	Rarely
B. Non-Print Materials	2.04	1.78	2.12	1.94	Rarely
1. Open Access Books	2.22	1.81	2.11	2.10	Rarely
2. Open Access Journals	2.13	1.81	2.13	2.04	Rarely
3. Open Access Thesis and Dissertations	2.06	1.82	2.18	2.00	Rarely
4. World Book Online (BCPL subscription)	2.00	1.72	2.09	1.91	Rarely
5. E-books (BCPL acquired e-books)	2.02	1.77	2.00	1.92	Rarely
6. CD-ROM (Accompanying material of books)	1.79	1.47	1.73	1.66	Rarely
7. Educational VCD and DVD	1.81	1.43	1.76	1.65	Rarely
8. Television	1.81	1.58	1.91	1.71	Rarely
9. Internet searching/browsing	2.87	2.77	3.38	2.84	Sometimes
10. Tech4eD (Technology for Education)	1.92	1.72	1.98	1.80	Rarely
11. Starbooks (Science and Technology Academic and Research-Based Openly Operated Kiosks)	1.86	1.69	2.04	1.76	Rarely
TOTAL WEIGHTED MEAN	2.11	1.78	2.25	2.01	RARELY

Group of Users: S=Student, U=Unemployed, E=Employed

Mean range: 3.50-4.00=Always; 2.50-3.49=Sometimes; 1.50-2.49=Rarely; 1.00-1.49=Never

and entertainment/recreation needs. Also, library users prefer browsing the internet by simply clicking the mouse rather than browsing books from the shelves. Whenever they require information, they turn to the internet as their main source. A possible reason is that the internet is easily accessible and convenient in providing users with a wide range of information sources to choose from, such as news websites, blogs, and social media platforms. Additionally, using the internet is often more cost-effective than using traditional sources of information. Aside from computers connected to the internet available at the public library, library users can also bring their laptops, and use their cell phones and connect to library's Wi-Fi. This proves beneficial to library users who do not have access to the internet at home.

The result of this study indicates that library users maximize the use of the free internet at the public library for academic development, personal development, and entertainment/recreational needs. But, seven years ago, the internet was ranked sixth as the information resource used by respondents at the city library, while books/textbooks ranked first (Bernardo, 2016). The key findings of the study suggest that library users have changing needs. Furthermore, in this evolving digital age, it implies library users use the internet as their main source of information to fulfill their information needs.

The result of this study was supported by Kumah (2015) that the key

purpose of the preferences for internet use included quick access to information, an abundance amount of information available on the internet, and readily available information. Kingor, Njiraine, and Maina (2016) revealed that though the internet was placed as the second preference for some respondents, they provided an array of compelling reasons for why they opted for the internet as a source of information. Some of the reasons they gave referred to are faster retrieval of information, access without any restrictions on place or a period of time, more accessible and flexible content, being able to access a large number of information quickly, and easy access to information whenever there is an internet connection. However, some library users do not have internet access at home. The study by Mojapelo (2019) discovered that the three public libraries offer free internet connection to library users and they benefit from using the free internet to fulfill all sorts of informational needs since they don't have an internet connection at home. Similarly, Pew Research Center (2014) data shows that most American citizens use free internet access at their public libraries because they don't have internet access and a computer in their homes. It was discovered that internet access at the public library is important for them. The New York Times report also talked about data analysis from the New York Public Library that revealed most library users who use the public library's computers and internet don't have access to it at home. The public library continues providing internet access and upgrading its speed to cater to the needs of library users. As also observed, most

library users suggested increasing the internet speed since they bring their laptops, and tablets, and use their cellular phones. As Kinney (2010) stated that public libraries play a vital role in offering free internet access to their communities. Also, the internet can access in utilizing public services and hunting for jobs.

The second most used information resource is reference books and books/textbooks. Even with the internet becoming more prevalent, reference books and books/textbooks remain vital source of information for library users. They value authority, quality, reliability, accuracy, and in-depth information on a wide range of topics, and are often written by experts in the field. It also provides access to information that may not be available on the internet or in digital formats, such as rare or out-of-print books. They turn to books if they cannot find the information they need on the internet. Additionally, the public library often has access to specialized collections of books, such as academic, research-based, or historical materials, that may not be available in digital formats. Furthermore, some library users prefer the physical experience of reading books and printed materials. The public library provides an invaluable service by making those library resources available.

The result of this study implies that print materials like reference books, books, and textbooks remain essential for library users that fulfill academic development, personal development, and entertainment/recreational needs. This is confirmed by the study of Parmar, Patel, and Parmar (2021) that most American

adults ages eighteen and older remain reading books remain and most popular. Despite the growing popularity of electronic books, print continues to be the preferred format for American readers. Even though the internet is widely used, reference books/textbook remains valuable for students. Likewise, the majority of library users preferred to use printed information resources as their source of information needs (Kingor, Njiraine, and Maina, 2016). In addition, the study by Devi Archana, and Babu (2021) discovered that there is a high percentage that print materials, such as textbooks, reports, and print journals, are still preferred by students from all three academic libraries. Furthermore, these resources are used by library users in updating subject knowledge and are information-rich materials that fulfill the information needs of the users.

Theses and dissertations are the third most used following the internet and reference books, books/textbooks. As part of the public library's special collection, these resources are part of the repository for unpublished theses and dissertations of the various universities in the city. Also, theses and dissertations highlight different aspects of knowledge in different areas.

Writing theses and dissertations is part of students' curriculum from high school to college, including graduate school. It is a school requirement and part of completing a degree. For library users, theses and dissertations serve as valuable sources of information for their research and studies. They turn to use these library resources to help them complete their research study and improve

their research work. They need to gather related literature to support research topics. In addition, these resources offer a platform for students to do in-depth research on a topic and present their findings comprehensively. They can use it to discuss new ideas, challenge existing theories and provide alternative perspectives. Furthermore, they have the opportunity and freedom to explore in-depth research on a topic of their choice.

Considering that theses and dissertations are the third most used resources by library users, denotes that some library users will likely use theses and dissertations to fulfill school requirements related to research work. They also perceived that there are available theses and dissertations to help them with academic development.

Similarly, Ekong and Ogunode (2022), suggest that thesis/dissertations are also highly used information resources by students, but not to the extent of the aforementioned highly used information resources. Furthermore, theses and dissertations remain to play an essential role in producing new data and information and serving as a base for improving students' abilities in a variety of study subject matter (Keshavarz and Shekari, 2020).

The least utilize media and information resource is educational CDs/VCDs. These resources are available in the Internet Section but only a few computers have DVD-ROM drives, and Audio-visual Room Section is still under development, so these resources are underutilized. Being the least used library

resources, library users are not likely to use them much or are unaware of these resources, and especially that educational videos can be found online. Similar to the study by Ekong and Ogunode (2022), CD-ROM databases and audio-visuals are among the library's least-used information resources.

Level of Competency in Media and Information Skills of Library Users

Level of competency refers to your ability to successfully complete a task while applying the required skills. This study measures library users' competency in accessing, evaluating, and using media and information resources. The results are checklist types taken by library users in the public library. General results show in Table 10 that library users have intermediate competency levels in media and information (mean = 3.04) across all skills namely access to (mean = 2.94), evaluation of (mean = 3.01), and use of (mean = 3.16) media and information.

Library users are moderately confident in their skills and abilities in accessing, using, and evaluating library resources. Library users' highest competency is the use of media and information resources. This competency indicates the ability to use information effectively, ethically, and legally for their particular purpose. It was a good sign that library users knew where to use the information they obtain from the public library. This shows that library users know why they visit the public library and where to use the information they have gathered such as students use it for academic development while unemployed

Table 10. General competency of library users in media and information skills

SKILL	WEIGHTED MEAN	LEVEL
1. Access to media and information	2.94	Intermediate
2. Evaluation of media and information	3.01	Intermediate
3. Use of media and information	3.16	Intermediate
TOTAL WEIGHTED MEAN	3.04	INTERMEDIATE

Mean range: 3.50-4.00=Advance; 2.50-3.49=Intermediate; 1.50-2.49=Basic; 1.00-1.49=Poor

and employed are for personal development. Findings show that library users have the necessary skills to utilize library resources. They can take the knowledge they gain from library resources and apply it to their own research and learning needs. This will enable them to generate creative and new knowledge. In spite of this, there skills that needs to be improved since their level of competency in the use of media and information sources is intermediate.

Evaluation of media and information resources ranks second to library users' competency. The library users assessed themselves at an intermediate level in the evaluation of media and information resources. The results demonstrated that library users were moderately confident in their ability to evaluate media and information. Despite the variation of library resources available at the public library, library users can decide if library resources are appropriate for their particular needs. They can determine if the library resources cover their topic of interest and if it is appropriate to include in their research. They consider the credibility, reliability, validity, accuracy, and authority of the library resources

they obtain. Although the results were regarded as intermediate, there are still indications that library users need to improve their skills in evaluating media and information resources to enhance their research skills.

Library users' least important competency is accessing media and information resources. According to Udo, Ben, Afaha, and Yusuf (2021), accessibility skills are regarded as searching and choosing important information out of multiple diversified internet sources using technologies like mobile phones, televisions, and computers and of a certain level to access these media contents are needed. The level of competency of library users in users in accessing media and information is intermediate. Library users may be adept at accessing library resources, such as searching for books, browsing the internet, and navigating online resources. They have the ability to find library resources, but may not have the advanced skills required to find information more effectively, such as understanding search techniques and researching topic. This has to do with the utilization of media and information resources by library users. Library users are most likely to use the internet in general. The internet provides an abundance of information but it can often be overwhelming for library users. Curated online links and resources for easy access to scholarly journals and e-books are not widely used. Most library users do not explore other resources to use for their academic and research needs.

It summarizes that library users have intermediate competencies in

accessing, using, and evaluating media and information resources. This means that library users may have the skills to locate and access library resources, evaluate the accuracy and quality of the information. This is important, as it allows library users to make informed decisions about the resources they use. However, the results also demonstrate that library users themselves are not so proficient with the competency, as they see room for improvement.

Results imply that most library users do not fully possess all the skills and abilities necessary for accessing, evaluating, and using media and information resources. The level of competency of library users is intermediate, it suggests that there are certain skills that need to be improved.

As mentioned by Tibaldo (2021), an intermediate competency level equates to an average level, it can still be enhanced to guarantee that one has skills in global MIL. The level of competence will be improved with more exposure to different media and information resources. This confirms the findings of Topal and Budak (2019) that the level of information literacy of those who frequently use information resources is higher than those who almost never use them. Furthermore, the skills in MIL are not natural or innate skills and abilities. They need to be learned using systematic procedures and approaches in schools, libraries, and other organizations where research is conducted (Rusiana and Naparota, 2021).

Level of Competency Along with Access to Media and Information Resources

The access element has to do with having the ability to access, retrieve, and save media texts using the right technologies. Information and content from libraries, personal files, museums, and other sources that may be physically or electronically kept are also retrievable, in addition to using the internet (Tibaldo, 2022). Library users' competency along with access to media and information resources (total weighted mean = 2.94) was explored through seven items, which are presented in Table 11. The highest access competency is 'selecting the most appropriate methods and/or database for meeting the information needs' (mean = 3.03).

The library users are moderately confident in this competency which is also a positive sign. This competency is significant because different types of media and information resources require different search methods. Most library users assess that they are capable of selecting the right search methods or tools for finding the information they need. By properly utilizing the right search methods and information sources, they can quickly locate the specific information they need. Library users can use the online public access catalog to locate the library resources they need. They can use search engines, online databases, or online resources to find scholarly articles and ask for help from librarians. Also, most library users know what resources are available at the public library.

Table 11. Library users' competency in the access to media and information

ACCESS	S	U	E	WEIGHTED MEAN	LEVEL
1. Selecting the most appropriate methods and/or database for meeting my information needs	2.91	3.15	3.28	3.03	Intermediate
2. Constructing and executing effectively designed search strategies to find out my required information from print or digital	2.78	3.13	3.09	2.92	Intermediate
3. Retrieving information using a variety of methods	2.84	3.11	3.22	2.97	Intermediate
4. Refining the search strategy if necessary	2.75	3.16	3.20	2.92	Intermediate
5. Using appropriate hardware/software to extract and manage located information	2.82	3.16	3.02	2.94	Intermediate
6. Recording all pertinent references of information sources for current and future need	2.75	3.09	3.07	2.88	Intermediate
TOTAL WEIGHTED MEAN	2.81 ^B	3.13 ^A	3.14 ^A	2.94	INTERMEDIATE
$F = 13.837^*$ $p = 0.000$					

Group of Users: S=Student, U=Unemployed, E=Employed

Mean range: 3.50-4.00=Advance; 2.50-3.49=Intermediate; 1.50-2.49=Basic; 1.00-1.49=Poor

*significant at 0.05 level; means labeled with different letters are significantly different from each other

Although library users have intermediate competencies, the results also indicate that their skills can be improved. The results indicate that the more skills library users have the more efficiently they can access library resources. It

suggests that library users may be able to improve their ability to access library resources if they are given more training and guidance.

The findings of this study are similar to the study by Ahmad (2017) that library users as researchers have satisfactory information literacy skills. The majority of the researchers can build up their search techniques to discover the information they need, can select appropriate databases and methods to search for the information they need, and can construct and execute effective search strategies. In line with the study by Gados and Lascano (2021) revealed that most students are adept at searching for their information needs out of the collections available in the library. This implies that they are knowledgeable enough to use the collection of the library. However, there is still room for improvement to become highly competent in using the information sources of the library. Furthermore, library users' MIL will be improved if they keep practicing and joining training on enhancing skills in MIL. This is confirmed in the study by Zhao, Luo, Sabina, and Pillon (2023) that receiving information literacy training improves one's information literacy abilities. Students who undergo information literacy training scored higher than students who had not received training. They have stronger information literacy skills in searching electronic resources and academic databases. Furthermore, the knowledge of librarians can help students or library users to improve their competency.

The library users are least competent in 'recording all pertinent references of information sources for current and future use' (mean = 2.88), which is interpreted as an intermediate skill. Library users may fail to keep track of the media and information resources they utilized, resulting in them forgetting what they previously used and how to do the proper citation. The possible reason is, library users may not be interested in tracking what library resources they have acquired for personal recordkeeping, but rather, they may just want to find the resources they need and use them without worrying about keeping track of what they're using. However, recording all pertinent references is essential to trace information resources used in any research activity.

The findings imply that library users must learn how to record all pertinent references to information sources for future needs. It suggests that keeping records will make it easier to verify and validate research. Keeping track of the sources used can ensure the accuracy and reliability of the research.

The finding is similar to the study by Ahmad (2017) that one of the least competencies of researchers is recording all pertinent references to information sources for current and future needs. It is possible that some researchers did not keep a record of the information resources they selected and utilized. It was mentioned by the University of New South Wales (2022) referencing is a means to present proof to back up statements and claims while doing assignments. Keeping track of all the sources utilized while reading and conducting research is

the greatest approach to ensure that citations are accurate. Furthermore, providing references for sources you used also lends credibility to your work, especially if you use reliable and authoritative sources (Castleton University, n.d.).

The results of this study also revealed that there exists a highly significant difference in level of competence on access to media and information resources among the three group of library users ($F = 13.837, p < 0.01$). Moreover, the post-hoc analysis using Tukey HSD showed that unemployed (mean = 3.14^A) and employed (mean = 3.13^A) library users have higher competency in access to media and information resources than students (mean = 2.81^B).

Unemployed individuals demonstrated the highest level of competency in accessing media and information resources among library users. Unemployed include college graduates, senior citizens, and out-of-school youth. During the study, the majority of unemployed individuals in this group were college graduates (27.80%). Along with the unemployed group, the percentage of college graduates is ninety-eight percent (98%). College graduates gained media and information competency during their academic days at their respective schools and universities. Even after they have completed their formal education, they can continue to gain knowledge and skills by engaging in self-directed learning, such as reading books and articles at the public library. In addition, they might also look for work which indicates that they are also dealing with information on how to land employment. They are studying which job skills are in demand, how to

ace an interview, how to write a successful resume, and how to navigate the job market information that are essential in landing a job. Also, this helps them to have the highest level of competency since they already have the specific media and information resources that they will access. Furthermore, it aligns with their ultimate purpose which is to review for the incoming board and licensure exams. This indicates they have a main focus and specific area of media and information resources to utilize.

The employed population consists of those working in the public sector (4.01%), the private sector (3.74%), and the self-employed (4.55%), who gained their abilities and skills during their formal education. They might have also used the public library before they passed their licensure and board examination for their chosen career. Though they are working they find time to visit the public library and utilize the media and information they need. They may be seeking to gain more knowledge and skills that can help them in their career. They seek library resources for their master's degree as they enhance their skills while doing their research and academic work. Also, they have less time to use the public library than the unemployed.

Among the three groups of library users, the students have the least level of competency in accessing media and information resources. This is because students are still in the process of learning and may not be as competent as unemployed and employed. This group of students consists of high school

(13.37%), college students (40.38%), and graduate school (5.67%) Since the purpose of students in utilizing media and information resources is for academic development, it is not only one subject they are focusing on. Students often need to access multiple sources, some of which may come from outside of the classroom like the public library. They might access different topics to fulfill their school requirement.

The findings indicate that the unemployed have a higher level of competency in access to media and information resources than the employed and students. Unemployed competency differs from that of employed and students. Travis (2011) revealed why non-students gained more information literacy skills. Respondents gain information literacy from college which has a significant impact on their careers. In addition, the respondents were asked 'What kinds of information do they frequently look for at work? The study discovered that the most frequently mentioned information sources they used at work were empirical research and current news. Furthermore, the results also show that while they work, they still deal with information. At the same time, this enhances their information literacy skills.

Level of Competency Along with Evaluation to Media and Information Resources

Evaluation comes next after access. Evaluation means assessing media and information sources you discover. Assessing each source's quality is essential to determining the importance of the information it offers. As observed in Table 12

there were seven items identified to explore library users' competency in the evaluation of media and information resources. According to the research outcomes, library users have intermediate competency in the evaluation of media and information resources (total weighted mean = 3.01). The results showed that the majority of library users had the highest proficiency when 'determining whether the information received is valuable or not' (mean = 3.09). Library users had the least proficiency when 'determining whether the information needed is accomplished or the initial query requires revision' (mean = 2.91).

There are various resources of information available at the public library but library users can make an informed decision about whether the information they seek is valuable or not. By considering the source and context of the information, they can judge if the information is appropriate and useful to their field of study and research endeavors. Library users have their own way or criteria to determine if the information is valuable or not. Though library users can decide on the information to use there is a certain thought that the information they seek is enough to accomplish the needed information because this does not require them to re-evaluate their search. A possible reason for this is when the amount of information overwhelms them, they might choose to settle for what they have found instead of continuing the search.

From this, the key findings revealed that library users have an intermediate level competencies but the results also demonstrate that there are skills that can be

Table 12. Library User's Competency in the Evaluation of Media and Information

EVALUATION	S	U	E	WEIGHTED MEAN	LEVEL
1. Summarize the main ideas to be extracted from the information gathered	2.96	3.24	3.26	3.08	Intermediate
2. Examine and compare information gathered from various sources to evaluate reliability, validity, accuracy, authority etc.	2.96	3.16	3.37	3.07	Intermediate
3. Synthesize main ideas to construct new concepts for my own academic work	2.89	3.07	3.13	2.97	Intermediate
4. Compare new knowledge with prior knowledge in determining the value added, contradictions, or other unique characteristics of the information	2.85	3.10	3.15	2.96	Intermediate
5. Determine whether the information received is valuable or not	2.99	3.24	3.28	3.09	Intermediate
6. Validate my understanding and interpretation of the information through discussion with other individuals, teachers, subject-area experts, etc.	2.92	3.14	3.28	3.03	Intermediate
7. Determine whether the information needed is accomplished or initial query needs to be revised	2.76	3.10	3.17	2.91	Intermediate
TOTAL WEIGHTED MEAN	2.90 ^B	3.15 ^A	3.24 ^A	3.01	INTERMEDIATE
	F = 9.569*		p = 0.000		

Group of Users: S=Student, U=Unemployed, E=Employed

Mean range: 3.50-4.00=Advance; 2.50-3.49=Intermediate; 1.50-2.49=Basic; 1.00-1.49=Poor

*significant at 0.05 level; means labeled with different letters are significantly different from each other

improved. This implies that the higher the level of library users' competency is, the more able to evaluate information accurately. It suggests that library users may be able to improve their ability to evaluate library resources. This is if they are more exposed to or equipped with standards for evaluating information sources as they assess the information they have.

The result of this study is similar to Rusiana and Naparota (2021), Tibaldo (2021) and Kingor, Njiraine, and Maina (2016) in that student have a good and intermediate level of evaluation competency, but it can be upgraded, which can be developed over time. Topal and Budak (2019) in order to improve students' information literacy skills, practical training programs are created by libraries to assist students to enhance their skills in access to a wide range of library resources. The findings of Karimi, Ashrafi-Rizi, Papi, Shahrzadi, and Hassanzadeh (2015) confirmed that the training was effective in enhancing students' information literacy. The student's knowledge of information scores was below average; after the training, they greatly improved after training. Also, the impact of education has gained the ability to critically evaluate information and its sources. Another way of educating students is the creation of method or guide for evaluating information sources. Educators and librarians can provide assistance to students in the form of a checklist and guide to evaluating information sources. This method is an example of that proposed by Mandalios (2013), who introduced the adoption of the acronym 'RADAR' (Relevance,

Authority, Date, Appearance, and Reason for writing) approach to evaluating information sources. This may be employed to evaluate any information source. They discovered RADAR to be simple to comprehend, remember, and utilize while browsing the internet for information for their homework. The extent to which it assisted them in making wise internet decisions and it was pertinent in research.

The results of this study also revealed that there exists a significant difference in level of competence on evaluation of media and information among three group of library users ($F = 9.569$, $p < 0.01$). Moreover, it revealed that unemployed (mean = 3.24^A) and employed (mean = 3.15^A) library users have higher competency in the evaluation of media and information resources than students (mean = 2.90^B).

As unemployed people have a higher level of proficiency in accessing media and information sources, they are also more likely to be able to assess their effectiveness. They are more capable of determining the reliability, validity, and accuracy of the media and information resources. They also know if the resources are valuable or not. Furthermore, it aligns with their personal development purpose which their focus is to evaluate the learning resources that will help them to pass their board and licensure exams. They want to make sure they are using the most up-to-date and accurate learning materials to prepare for their exams. This ensures that they are best prepared to answer questions accurately and

confidently. They also read library resources which help them to develop their personal interests and read other books that are related to what they are reviewing.

The employed group has competence in the evaluation of media and information resources at least as high as the unemployed group. They can evaluate library resources that will enable them to stay up to date with the latest trends and developments in their field of work which will help them to gain competencies.

Among library users, students are least competent in using media and information resources. This follows with the highest utilized by students which is the internet. It can be the information found on internet can be difficult to choose the ones that are most relevant and helpful to their research, and they can become overwhelmed with the information.

The findings indicate that the unemployed have a higher level of competency in the evaluation of media and information resources than the employed and students. Unemployed competency differs from that of employed and students.

One significant factor why unemployed or employed individuals possess a higher competency level is the continuous application of the skills they have and the experience dealing with information resources. The results of the study by Travis (2011) revealed that respondents employ research skills at work, value and make use of the library resources, and most crucially, value the knowledge and

and abilities they acquire from locating, analyzing, and using information.

Level of Competency Along with the Use of Media and Information Resources

After exploring different aspects of media and information literacy through access and evaluation, library resources must then be used for the reason that the information was required. The use of media and information resources by library users was analyzed using seven items from the research survey. As shown in Table 13, the overall mean in the use of media and information literacy skills by library users is also intermediate (total weighted mean = 3.16). All items had intermediate skills. Along with the use of media and information resources, the highest is 'know how to avoid plagiarism and use information ethically' (mean = 3.40), followed by 'able to follow laws, regulations, institutional policies, and etiquette related to use of information resources' (mean = 3.27).

The study revealed that library users can understand how to use media and information resources. They are aware of the consequences of plagiarism and take steps to ensure that information is used properly. They understand also the importance of giving credit when referencing information from other sources and can identify when something is plagiarized. Besides, they can adhere to laws, regulations, institutional policies, and etiquette related to information resources. This demonstrates that library users are aware of social and scholarly responsibilities in using media and information resources. They have the

Table 13. Library users' competency in the use of media and information

USE	S	U	E	WEIGHTED MEAN	LEVEL
1. Know how to apply new and prior information to my task	3.07	3.28	3.30	3.16	Intermediate
2. Know how to maintain my notes of activities related to the information seeking evaluating and communication process	2.98	3.31	3.33	3.12	Intermediate
3. Know how to communicate the outcome or performance created from the extracted information in effective manners	2.80	3.17	3.22	2.96	Intermediate
4. Able to understand the ethical, legal, and socio-economic issues surrounding information and information technology	2.89	3.23	3.28	3.03	Intermediate
5. Able to follow laws, regulations, institutional policies, and etiquette related to use of information resources	3.17	3.44	3.37	3.27	Intermediate
6. Know how to cite (give reference) to the consulted information sources in appropriate manner	3.12	3.36	3.20	3.20	Intermediate
7. Know how to avoid plagiarism and use information ethically	3.32	3.51	3.48	3.40	Intermediate
TOTAL WEIGHTED MEAN	3.05 ^B	3.33 ^A	3.31 ^A	3.16	INTERMEDIATE
$F = 10.084^*$				$p = 0.000$	

Group of Users: S=Student, U=Unemployed, E=Employed

Mean range: 3.50-4.00=Advance; 2.50-3.49=Intermediate; 1.50-2.49=Basic; 1.00-1.49=Poor

*significant at 0.05 level; means labeled with different letters are significantly different from each other

knowledge necessary to use them responsibly and effectively, as well as to recognize the importance of intellectual property rights and the need to acknowledge the authors of the consulted sources.

The results show that library users know how to use media and information resources for academic development, personal development, and entertainment/recreation. They might learn their skills from formal education and personal experience. With the skills they have, they can use media and information resources that are suited to their needs and they will use them to their fullest potential. This helps to ensure that resources are used for the intended purpose and not wasted. Also, exposure to media and information resources can develop knowledge and skills and gain a better understanding of the world around them.

Even though library users have an intermediate level of competency, the results also show that some skills can still be improved. This implies that the higher library users' information literacy competency, the higher their use of media and information resources for their particular purpose. It is essential for library users to develop their media and information literacy competency to make the most of library resources and prevent misappropriation.

The result is likely similar to the study by Ahmad (2017) in which respondents claimed that were able to follow institutional policies, regulations, laws, and etiquette related to the use of media and information resources.

Undoubtedly, the ability to use information ethically, cite sources, and observe fair use, is an important part of MI. The result indicates that the respondents can use information ethically and legally. In addition, Rusiana and Naporata (2019) and Tibaldo (2019) show that high students and college students have good and intermediate levels of competencies in MIL as interpreted at the same level. Although high school students have media and information literacy subjects, the results suggest that it is necessary to facilitate student competencies in media and information literacy, especially in research areas. This can be achieved through supporting and empowering students as they use the library's resources for their academic pursuits. Also, the integration of MIL programs into the college curriculum will have a significant impact on skill development. The results were consistent with those of Soleymani (2014) found that there was a strong beneficial relationship between students' academic performance and information literacy at Isfahan University of Medical Sciences. Information literacy skills help students in their academic endeavors. It is necessary to provide them with skills related to information literacy to improve their academic performance. Furthermore, Tropol and Budak (2019) cited Keten (2012), the presence of information literacy programs created by librarians will enable assist individuals who need the information to learn how to utilize the information effectively, solve their problems quickly and simply, and make the right decisions. Moreover, the availability of information resources affects the information literacy of an

individual. It was determined in the study by Akpovire, Olawoyin, Adebayo, and Ugwunwa (2019) that information literacy skill serves as a motivation for the use of information resources. In the absence of competence, there will be no interest and this can negatively impact the use of information resources. This implies that students who possess strong information literacy skills use information resources more frequently.

Library users showed the least skill among the seven items, 'knowing how to communicate the outcomes or performances created from the extracted information effectively' (mean = 2.96), and at an intermediate level. Library users can convey the information they gather in an effective and efficient way. They can consolidate the insight they gained from the media and information resources but not to the extent of the aforementioned advanced level. Library users might have fewer media and information skills in communicating the outcome or performance created from the extracted information in an effective manner. The possible reason is that they may not have the necessary skills or knowledge to effectively communicate their findings. They may lack the ability to analyze and interpret the data they extract. As a result, they are unable to confidently and accurately explain the significance of their findings.

This implies that library users have less ability to communicate what they sought in a clear and concise way. The study finds comparable with Anunobi and Udem's (2015) study that Library and Information Science postgraduate students

possess moderate competency in 'communicating and presenting information to others in the appropriate and usable format'. This skill was also the least competency students possessed along with the ability to use information. When it comes to information exchange, using the right digital technology at the right time is essential. It is important that students learn when to use different forms of communication, such as social media and text messages. It is also important for them to learn how to organize their thoughts in a way that others can understand them (Let's Talk Science, n.d.).

The results of this study also revealed that competency levels have a significant difference in level of competence on use of media and information resources among the three library users ($F = 10.084$, $p < 0.01$). Moreover, it showed that employed (mean = 3.33^A) and unemployed (mean = 3.31^A) library users have higher competency in the use of media and information resources than students (mean = 3.05^B).

Even though the employed group has fewer skills and abilities when it comes to accessing and evaluating media and information when compared to the unemployed yet they have a higher level of competency when it comes to using these resources. Since they are working, they are more exposed to the media and information surrounding them and they are dealing with it as part of their career. Most likely they know already what media and information resources to use. It aligns with their top goal of personal development. Moreover, this group of

library users is professionals; they are observing the concerns and issues in using media and information resources.

The competence of the unemployed group in using media and information resources is near to that of the employed, but they are higher than students. This might be because they are less likely to use the media and information resources found in the public library. It follows from the results that they do not regularly use public library resources. As observed, they also likely bring review materials that are up-to-date and comprehensive and the resources they want to use might not be available at the public library. This means that they are able to get more information and better prepare for the exam by bringing their own materials. Also, their main purpose is personal development, which makes sense since they only use it for themselves. The difference is that students need it for school requirements, while employed people may need it for work purposes.

Students are least in the level of competency in using media and information resources among the group of library users. It proves that they are still learning to improve their competency. Also, media and information literacy are included in the curriculum of DepEd in high school. This might help them to improve their competence and continue to improve it as they go to college.

The findings indicate that the employed have a higher level of competency in the use of media and information resources than the unemployed and students. Employed competency differs from that of unemployed and students.

The result of this study is supported by the findings of Ornopia (2019) that the employees of the Philippine News Agency and the Philippine Information Agency have already advanced competencies in MIL. They enhance their competency through training which leads to an advanced level of competency. Moreover, learning does not stop when you are employed, but it continues even when you are working. Furthermore, having the necessary competency will lead to getting a job. The result is in line with the study by Travis (2011), who found that the majority of respondents considered finding information an essential part of their work. They believe that getting hired in their current position was influenced by their information literacy skills.

Based on the results, it appears that the more exposed to different media and information resources and the more experience dealing with them, the higher the level of competency. Likewise, nonstop learning is the process of continually acquiring new skills and abilities. This can take on various forms, ranging from formal education to casual social learning (Chiyo, 2021). As Sword (2021) stated that the process of continuous learning is acquiring new skills and knowledge that develop over time. This will help you develop both professionally and personally, realize your highest potential, and open doors to new opportunities. Moreover, UNESCO (2013) highlights that MIL competencies exist in a continuum of competencies that can be enhanced and developed through time.

Summary

The salient findings of the study are summarized as follows.

1. Most library users mainly use media and information sources for academic development purposes and followed by personal development and entertainment/recreation purposes.

Along with academic development, library users mainly go to the library to study or review their lessons for incoming periodical examinations and to read references that would supplement their studies or school requirements.

Anchoring personal development, the main purpose of library users makes use of the public library to review for their incoming licensure/board/civil service examination.

Most of the respondents do not view the public library as a place for entertainment/recreation. All statements were interpreted as ‘Rarely’ and there is no statement was interpreted as at least ‘Sometimes’.

2. Both print materials and non-print materials have equal utilization. Out of the seventeen (17) library resources listed, only reference books and internet searching/browsing are utilized to the extent of sometimes, the rest of the library resources are utilized to the extent of rarely.

3. Students, unemployed, and employed have an intermediate level of competency in accessing, evaluating, and using media and information resources. They are moderately confident in their ability and skills.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the study's conclusions and recommendations. Conclusions are drawn based on the interpretations and findings of the study, and recommendations are based on those findings. It provides a portrait of the level of competency in media and information literacy among library users of the Baguio City Public Library.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The Baguio City Public Library serves more as a resource center for academic development and least for entertainment/leisure.
2. Reference books, books/textbooks, and the internet are sometimes used, but other library resources are rarely used.
3. Library users possess an intermediate level of competency in accessing, evaluating, and utilizing media and information resources.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were drawn from the conclusions:

1. The public library may create a program and activities to showcase the library's entertainment/recreational role (Appendix E).

2. The Baguio City Public Library needs high-speed internet to meet library users' growing needs and needs to be met with enough bandwidth to support it.

3. The Baguio City Public Library may continue to provide free seminars related to media and information literacy.

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APPENDIX A

Letter for the Respondents

Dear Respondents,

The undersigned is a graduate student of Benguet State University and is currently undertaking research entitled “Media and Information Literacy Skills of Baguio City Public Library Users” in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree, Master in Library and Information Science. It will also serve as a basis to further develop the library services.

In this regard, may I seek your kind assistance by answering the survey questionnaire promptly and honestly? Rest assured that your responses will be used solely for educational and development purposes only.

Thank you very much for giving this matter to your attention and for your cooperation and support.

Respectfully yours,

(Sgd)MAY JOYCE M. DULNUAN
Researcher

(Sgd) RUSSELL B. DOLENDO, PhD
Adviser

APPENDIX B

Questionnaire

Direction: Please select an appropriate response by indicating with a check (✓) in the applicable box/and per instruction.

Profile of the Respondents

Status:

 Student

 High School

 College

 Graduate School

 Employed

 Public Employee

 Private Employee

 Self-Employed

 Unemployed

 Senior Citizen

 College Graduate

 Parent

 Out-of School Youth

II. What do you usually do when you visit the library? How often do you use the library for each purpose stated below? Please Check (✓) those applicable to you.

Legend (four-point scale)

- | | | |
|---|-----------|---|
| 4 | Always | I spend my time (purpose) 5 to 6 times a week in the library. |
| 3 | Sometimes | I spend my time (purpose) 3 to 4 times a week in the library. |
| 2 | Rarely | I spend my time (purpose) 1 to 2 times a week in the library |
| 1 | Never | I never spend my time (purpose) in the library. |

Purpose/s	4	3	2	1
A. Academic Development				
1. To study or review my lessons for incoming quarterly/semester examination.				
2. To consult books and obtain other relevant information for my research or assignment.				
3. To answer my online activities and do my school requirement.				
4. To read references that will supplement my studies or school requirement.				
5. To access online resources.				
B. Personal Development				
1. To explore the available library references and enhance my knowledge.				
2. To learn new skills through reading.				
3. To review for my incoming licensure/board/civil service examination				
4. To keep up to date with current events.				
5. To read books about inspiration.				
C. Entertainment or Recreation				
1. To read newspapers and magazines.				
2. To read fiction books.				
3. To watch the television.				
4. To pass leisure time by browsing the internet, connecting to Wi-Fi, or browsing YouTube and Facebook.				

III. The following are the list of media and information resources found at Baguio City Public Library. How often do you use the library resources available in every library section? Please Check (✓) those which you are using.

Legend (four-point scale)

- | | | |
|---|-------------------|--|
| 4 | Always Utilize | At all times I use the media and information resources. |
| 3 | Sometimes Utilize | I usually make use the media and information resources. |
| 2 | Rarely Utilize | I occasionally make use the media and information resources. |
| 1 | Not Utilize | I don't use the media and information resources at all. |

Media and Information Resources	Rating			
A. Print Materials	4	3	2	1
1. Reference Books, Books/Textbooks				
2. Newspaper and magazine				
3. Globes, Maps				
4. Brochure and Pamphlets				
5. Theses and Dissertation				
6. Fiction Books				
B. Non-Print Materials	4	3	2	1
1. Open Access Books (Links and resources curated on the BCPL website)				
2. Open Access Journals (Links and resources curated on the BCPL website)				
3. Open Access Thesis and Dissertations (Links and resources curated on the BCPL website)				
4. World Book Online (BCPL subscription)				
5. E-books (BCPL acquired e-books)				
6. CD-ROM (Accompanying material of books)				
7. Educational VCD and DVD				
8. Television				
9. Internet searching/browsing (Google/Yahoo)				
10. Tech4eD (Technology for Education)				
11. Starbooks (Science and Technology Academic and Research-Based Openly Operated Kiosks)				

IV. The following statements under each tenet will assess the level of your competencies in media and information literacy. Please rate yourself by putting a check mark (✓) in every item from 1-32 under the rating column based on the following criteria:

(This Part IV of the questionnaire is adapted from the study of Ahmad, 2017)

- | | | |
|---|--------------|---|
| 4 | Advance | I am extremely confident in my ability and skills. |
| 3 | Intermediate | I am moderately confident in my ability and skills |
| 2 | Basic | I am somewhat confident in my ability and skills. |
| 1 | Poor | I am not confident at all in my ability and skills. |

Level of Competencies	Rating			
1. Access to Media and Information Resources	4	3	2	1
a. I am capable of selecting the most appropriate methods and/or database for meeting my information needs.				
b. I am capable of constructing and executing effectively designed search strategies to find out my required information from print or digital.				
c. I am capable of retrieving information using a variety of methods.				
d. I am capable of refining the search strategy if necessary.				
e. I am capable of using appropriate hardware/software to extract and manage located information.				
f. I am capable of recording all pertinent references of information sources for current and future need.				
2. Evaluation of Media and Information Resources	4	3	2	1
a. I can summarize the main ideas to be extracted from the information gathered.				
b. I can examine and compare information gathered from various sources in order to evaluate reliability, validity, accuracy, authority etc.				
c. I can synthesize main ideas to construct new concepts for my own academic work.				

d. I can synthesize main ideas to construct new concepts for my own academic work.				
e. I can compare new knowledge with prior knowledge in determining the value added, contradictions, or other unique characteristics of the information.				
f. I can determine whether the information received is valuable or not?				
g. I can validate my understanding and interpretation of the information through discussion with other individuals, teachers, subject-area experts, etc.				
h. I can determine whether the information needed is accomplished or initial query needs to be revised.				
3. Use of Media and Information Resources	4	3	2	1
a. I know how to apply new and prior information to my task.				
b. I know how to maintain my notes of activities related to the information seeking evaluating and communication process.				
c. I know how to communicate the outcome or performance created from the extracted information in effective manners.				
d. I am able to understand the ethical, legal and socio-economic issues surrounding information and information technology.				
e. I am able to follow laws, regulations, institutional policies, and etiquette related to use of information resources.				
f. I know how to cite (give reference) to the consulted information sources in appropriate manner.				
g. I know how to avoid plagiarism and use information ethically.				

APPENDIX C

Letter of Permission

January 25, 2023

EASTER W. PABLO
City Librarian
Baguio City Public Library

Dear Ma'am

The undersigned is a graduate student of Benguet State University and is currently undertaking research entitled "Media and Information Literacy Skills of Baguio City Public Library Users" in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree, Master in Library and Information Science. The study aims to identify the media and information literacy skills and competencies of library users.

In this regard, may I request your approval to administer a survey questionnaire to library users from January 24, 2023, to February 24, 2023?

Thank you very much for your kind consideration.

Respectfully yours,

(Sgd.) MAY JOYCE M. DULNUAN
Researcher

Noted:

(Sgd.) RUSSELL B. DOLENDO, PhD
Adviser

Approved:

(Sgd.) EASTER W. PABLO
City Librarian

APPENDIX D

Reliability Coefficient

Table 1. Interpretation Scale for Reliability Coefficient

Interval	Interpretation
$\alpha \geq 0.70$	Reliable
$\alpha < 0.70$	Unreliable

Table 2. Reliability Coefficients

Construct	Cronbach's α	Interpretation
Purposes	0.83	Reliable
Media and Information Resources	0.94	Reliable
Level of Competencies	0.95	Reliable

Prepared for May Joyce M. Dulnuan
 by Jonas L. Depaynos, MAAS
 January 25, 2023

APPENDIX E

Entertainment/Recreation Activities
at Baguio City Public Library

Goal: To promote the entertainment/recreational role of the public library.

Activities	Objectives	Strategies	Schedule
<p>1. Board Games Battle</p> <p>The benefits of board games include contributing to critical thinking, keeping your mind sharp, strategic skills, enhancing social interaction, and just plain having enjoyment.</p>	<p>a. To encourage library users in active participation through board games activities of the public library.</p> <p>b. To maximize the fun of board games.</p>	<p>Creation and announcement of public library activities through the following:</p> <p>a. Facebook posting</p> <p>b. Bulletin board display</p> <p>c. Digital display</p>	Monthly
<p>2. Book Lovers Club Talks</p> <p>Books and readers are a great way to engage them in the library that builds a reading culture.</p>	<p>a. To provide a wonderful forum for library users to talk about reading experiences and books.</p> <p>b. To strengthen the camaraderie of library users and the public library.</p>		Every last day of the Month
<p>3. Film Viewing</p> <p>Public libraries are not for books only but also, they offer an entertainment as well as educational activities like film viewing.</p>	<p>a. To enhance the usability and accessibility of the audio-visual materials of the public library while adding additional knowledge to the library users.</p> <p>b. To provide an entertainment space for library users.</p>		As requested by library users